

Kinetics and Mechanism of Ninhydrin Reaction with L-Proline

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Manuscript received 16 November 1992, revised 9 March 1993, accepted 23 April 1993

The composition of the product formed by the reaction of L-proline with ninhydrin has been determined using Job's method of continuous variation. Kinetics and mechanism of this reaction have been studied as a function of pH, temperature and ninhydrin concentration in the range of $(4.0-20.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. It follows pseudo-first order reaction path for the formation of carbon dioxide and enol betaine with respect to proline in presence of excess of ninhydrin concentration. The formation of two products takes place simultaneously through the concerted electronic mechanism. On the basis of the observed rate data, possible mechanism has been proposed.

In our previous studies^{1,2} on the interaction of various α -amino acids with ninhydrin it was reported that diketohydrindylidene diketohydrindamine (DYDA), a purple coloured product is formed. The interaction of ninhydrin was carried out with proline and it was found that a yellow coloured product (enolbetaine), quite different from DYDA, is formed. A number of methods for the spectrophotometric determination of proline³ have been developed by a number of investigators but no attempt has been made for kinetic and mechanistic studies of the reaction. Therefore, kinetics and mechanism of yellow product formed by the interaction of proline and ninhydrin are reported here.

Results and Discussion

The results of the evolution of the carbon dioxide and formation of enol betaine by the reaction of L-proline with ninhydrin can be summarised as follows : Job's method of continuous variations indicated that one mole of L-proline reacts with one mole of ninhydrin. The reaction follows an irreversible pseudo-first order reaction path for the formation of carbon dioxide and enol betaine with respect to L-proline in presence of excess of ninhydrin concentration. The rate constants (k_{obs}) were calculated by using a program developed for the computer VAX-11/780. Effect of [hydrogen ion] was studied in sodium acetate acetic acid buffer over the range 1.58×10^{-4} to $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ keeping other parameters constant. The rate of decarboxylation and formation of enol betaine was found to increase with decrease

in $[\text{H}^+]$ of the reaction medium. There is no effect of ionic strength on the rate constants. At fixed ionic strength (adjusted with KNO_3) the rate increases with the increase in temperature of the reaction mixture. The values of rate constants and activation parameters are given in Table 1 which show that the carbon dioxide and enol betaine are formed

TABLE 1—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR NINHYDRIN REACTION WITH L-PROLINE

[L-Proline] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [Ninhydrin] = $1.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 353 K

	E^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	log A min ⁻¹	$\times 10^2 k_{\text{obs}}$ min ⁻¹
For decarboxylation	39.01	83.76	36.07	4.56	6.14
For colour reaction	52.24	67.65	49.30	6.50	5.89

simultaneously. The effect of ninhydrin concentration was studied at a fixed [L-proline] = $6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and temperature 80° . The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—NINHYDRIN CONCENTRATION DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANTS FOR L-PROLINE REACTION

[L-Proline] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 353 K

$\times 10^2$ [Ninhydrin] mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^2 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ min}^{-1}$	
	For decarboxylation	For colour reaction
0.4	2.83	2.78
0.8	4.59	4.55
1.2	6.14	5.89
1.6	6.73	6.63
2.0	7.24	7.03

In the hydrogen ion concentration range studied the ionisation of L-proline is presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Under our experimental conditions ($[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) the concentration of anionic form of L-proline is negligible in comparison to zwitterionic form because K_{a2} of L-proline⁴ is 2.0×10^{-10} . The cationic and zwitterionic species are inactive towards the nucleophilic attack on carbonyl carbon of ninhydrin because these species have positive charge on nitrogen atom. The neutral form of L-proline is a reactive species.

The aqueous solution of ninhydrin exist in the following equilibrium state :

The anhydride form of ninhydrin is the only reacting species for the condensation with amino group. The probable mechanism which accounts for the rate data is given in Scheme 2. In this mechanism, the imino group of proline reacts with carbonyl group of ninhydrin to give intermediate (D). Enol betaine and carbon dioxide are formed as the products after the dehydration and decarboxylation of (D). On the basis of the proposed mechanism, the following kinetic equation has been derived,

$$\frac{d[P]}{dt} = \frac{d[CO_2]}{dt} =$$

$$\frac{k_1 k_3 K_{a1} K_D [\text{Ninhydrin}] [\text{L-Proline}]}{(k_2 + k_3) \left\{ [H^+] + K_{a1} + K_{a1} K_D + k_1 K_D K_{a1} [\text{Ninhydrin}] \right\}} \quad (1)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} =$$

$$\frac{k_1 k_3 K_{a1} K_D [\text{Ninhydrin}]}{(k_2 + k_3) \left\{ [H^+] + K_{a1} (1 + K_D) + k_1 K_D K_{a1} [\text{Ninhydrin}] \right\}} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) may be simplified by making the approximations $K_D \approx 10^5$, $1 + K_D \approx K_D$ and which is reduced to equation (3),

$$K_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 k_3 K_D [\text{Ninhydrin}]}{(k_2 + k_3) \left\{ \frac{[H^+]}{K_{a1}} + K_D + k_1 K_D [\text{Ninhydrin}] \right\}} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) on rearrangement gives equation (4),

$$1/k_{\text{obs}} = B_1 / [\text{Ninhydrin}] + B_2 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where, } B_1 = \frac{(k_2 + k_3) \left(\frac{[H^+]}{K_{a1}} + K_D \right)}{k_1 k_3 K_D}$$

$$\text{and } B_2 = \frac{(k_2 + k_3)}{k_3}$$

which shows a linear dependence of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Ninhydrin}]$ (Figs. 1 and 2). The addition reaction of any amino and imino compounds with carbonyl compound depends upon the $[H^+]$ on the reaction medium. Dehydration is also a acid-catalysed reaction.

Scheme 2

In the case of α -amino acid–ninhydrin reaction the adduct is visualised as undergoing a concerted electronic change to give a Schiff base which is hydrolysed to aldehyde and 2-aminoindandione. In

case of proline the hydrolysis of enol betaine is more difficult because the quaternary nitrogen is

Fig. 1. Linear dependence of $1/k_{obs}$ on $1/[Ninhydrin]$ for decarboxylation of L-proline with ninhydrin at $[L\text{-proline}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and temp. = 353 K.

fully substituted and prototropic rearrangement is not possible. Thus under our experimental condition, enol betaine is the end-product for the

Fig. 2. Linear dependence of $1/k_{obs}$ on $1/[Ninhydrin]$ for the colour reaction of L-proline with ninhydrin at $[L\text{-proline}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and temp. = 353 K.

reaction of proline and ninhydrin along with carbon dioxide.

Experimental

L-Proline (B.D.H.) and ninhydrin (S.R.L.) were used as such. Solutions of proline and ninhydrin were prepared in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer at different pH. pH measurements were made by using a Elico LI-10 pH meter. All the reagents were of A.R. grade. The requisite solutions of proline were placed in a three-necked reaction vessel fitted with a double-surface condenser to prevent evaporation. The reaction vessel was thermostated in an oil-bath to $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The reaction was then started by adding the requisite volume of ninhydrin solution and zero time was taken when half of the ninhydrin solution had been added. Pure nitrogen gas was bubbled through the reaction mixture for stirring as well as to maintain an inert atmosphere. Ionic strength of the reaction mixture was adjusted to the desired value by adding the required amount of potassium nitrate solution. The concentration of proline in the reaction vessel was $6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and that of ninhydrin was varied from 4.0×10^{-3} to $20.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The progress of reaction was followed spectrophotometrically by pipetting out aliquots of the reaction mixture at definite time intervals and measuring the optical density at 375 nm using an Elico CL-27 spectrophotometer.

Composition of the enol betaine (yellow colour) formed by the reaction of L-proline with ninhydrin was determined by Job's method of continuous variation. For this purpose, solutions of L-proline and ninhydrin were mixed, heated for 1 h and their absorbance measured at 375 nm. The rate of evolution of carbon dioxide was studied under the same conditions as those of enol betaine formation. Carbon dioxide was estimated by the method as described earlier.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M. A. Beg, Chairman, Department of Chemistry for facilities. Two of the authors (Z.K. and D.G.) are also thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial support.

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